

Tempered Fractional Integrals and Their Applications: New Euler-Maclaurin-Type Inequalities for Various Function Classes

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Abstract

In this study, we extend the results of Hezenci and Budak [1] by deriving new Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities using tempered fractional integrals for various function classes. Leveraging a key lemma for tempered fractional integrals, we establish inequalities for bounded functions and Lipschitzian functions, enhancing the scope of existing results in tempered fractional calculus. These new results generalize and enhance existing inequalities by providing a more comprehensive approach to tempered fractional calculus. Furthermore, several specific cases are examined to highlight the practical applications of these inequalities in numerical analysis and other fields.

1. Introduction and Preliminaries

The modern idea of convexity was initiated in the nineteenth century by Karl Hermann Amandus Schwarz, which has its roots in ancient Greek philosophy [8]. It is extensively useful in many branches of science and technology, primarily in operations research, finance, engineering, and computer science, especially where issues of optimization, defining a geometric property of sets or functions, and fractional integration are encountered. A mapping $F: [\omega, \rho] \rightarrow \mathfrak{R} \subset \mathfrak{R}$ is said to be a convex function if the given inequality holds:

$$tF(\omega) + (1-t)F(\rho) \geq F(t\omega + (1-t)\rho) \quad (1)$$

for all $\omega, \rho \in I, t \in [0, 1]$. Also, we say that F is concave, if the inequality (1) is reversed.

Significant research has demonstrated a close relationship between convexity theory and integral inequalities, emphasizing their importance in differential equations and applied mathematics. Some of these inequalities include the Euler-Maclaurin, Hermite Hadamard, Milne, Jensen, Gruss, Hölder, and Simpson types, which use the convexity principle to lead us to better conclusions. It helps us in other areas, such as differential equations, optimization techniques, and approximation theories. Such relationships are studied by researchers not only for the sake of promoting theory but also for the enhancement of problem-solving in various fields in scientific domains [1, 4, 34].

In [5], Dragomir formulated an estimation for the remainder in Simpson's quadrature formula, particularly concerning

bounded variation. In addition, he established the applications of this estimation within the framework of special means, encompassing both the logarithmic and identic mean. His foundational work offers important insights into numerical integration techniques and their connection with special means theory, representing an essential contribution to both theoretical and applied mathematics. With Riemann Liouville fractional integrals, Sitthiwiratham et al. [33] have investigated some Newton-type inequalities by involving convex functions and functions of bounded variation. Erden et al. [10] first proved an extended integral identity. For functions whose first derivative in absolute value at a given power is arithmetically-harmonically convex, several new integral inequalities of Newton's type are established using this new auxiliary result. Additionally, certain unique scenarios and applications to specific methods are examined. Utilizing local fractional integrals, Iftikhar et al. [22] provide a significant identity. Taking advantage of this identity, they investigated novel Newton-type inequalities for functions whose local fractional derivatives, in absolute value as well as certain powers, indicate generalized convexity. To learn more about the Newton-type inequality, which takes convex differentiable functions into account, please consult [14, 16, 17] and its references.

Gümüs et al. [15] presented several Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities for diverse classes of functions leveraging Riemann Liouville fractional integrals. In order to obtain specific error estimates for the Maclaurin quadrature rules, Dedic' et al. [7] offered a set of inequalities utilizing the

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Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities. In the context of differentiable convex functions, Hezenci and Budak established a novel equality. With the aid of this equality, many Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities are obtained [21]. For more details on this type of inequality, the reader is directed to [9, 11, 12, 27] and the references therein.

Simpson's rules can be stated as follows:

- The following formula represents Simpson's quadrature, also referred to as Simpson's 1/3 rule:

$$\int_{\omega}^{\rho} F(\eta) d\eta \approx \frac{\rho-\omega}{6} \left[F(\omega) + 4F\left(\frac{\omega+\rho}{2}\right) + F(\rho) \right]. \quad (2)$$

- The formula for Newton-Cotes quadrature, referred to as Simpson's second formula, can be stated in the following way [6]:

$$\int_{\omega}^{\rho} F(\eta) d\eta \approx \frac{\rho-\omega}{8} \left[F(\omega) + 3F\left(\frac{2\omega+\rho}{3}\right) + 3F\left(\frac{\omega+2\rho}{3}\right) + F(\rho) \right]. \quad (3)$$

- Based on the Maclaurin formula (as shown in [6]), the Maclaurin rule is equivalent to the corresponding dual Simpson's 3/8 formula:

$$\int_{\omega}^{\rho} F(\eta) d\eta \approx \frac{\rho-\omega}{8} \left[3F\left(\frac{5\omega+\rho}{6}\right) + 2F\left(\frac{\omega+\rho}{2}\right) + 3F\left(\frac{\omega+5\rho}{6}\right) \right]. \quad (4)$$

These formulas apply to any function F having a continuous fourth derivative across the interval $[\omega, \rho]$: (2), (3), and (4).

The following Newton-Cotes quadrature, frequently employed, includes a three-point Simpson's-type inequality:

Theorem 1. Given that $F: [\omega, \rho] \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}$ be a four times differentiable and continuous function on (ω, ρ) , and let $\|F^{(4)}\|_{\infty} = \sup_{\eta \in (\omega, \rho)} |F^{(4)}(\eta)| < \infty$. Then, the subsequent inequality is valid:

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[F(\omega) + 4F\left(\frac{\omega+\rho}{2}\right) + F(\rho) \right] - \frac{1}{\rho-\omega} \int_{\omega}^{\rho} F(\eta) d\eta \right| \leq \frac{1}{2880} \|F^{(4)}\|_{\infty} (\rho-\omega)^4.$$

According to the Simpson 3/8 inequality, the Simpson 3/8 rule is a recognized closed-type quadrature rule, stated in the following manner:

Theorem 2. Given that $F: [\omega, \rho] \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}$ is a function that is differentiable four times and continuous on (ω, ρ) , and $\|F^{(4)}\|_{\infty} = \sup_{\eta \in (\omega, \rho)} |F^{(4)}(\eta)| < \infty$. After that, one can see the following inequality:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[F(\omega) + 3F\left(\frac{2\omega+\rho}{3}\right) + 3F\left(\frac{\omega+2\rho}{3}\right) + F(\rho) \right] - \frac{1}{\rho-\omega} \int_{\omega}^{\rho} F(\eta) d\eta \right| \leq \frac{1}{6480} \|F^{(4)}\|_{\infty} (\rho-\omega)^4.$$

Originating in the Maclaurin formula, the Maclaurin rule is equivalent to the corresponding dual Simpson's 3/8 formula:

Theorem 3. Given that $F: [\omega, \rho] \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}$ is a function that is differentiable four times and continuous on (ω, ρ) , and let $\|F^{(4)}\|_{\infty} = \sup_{\eta \in (\omega, \rho)} |F^{(4)}(\eta)| < \infty$. Then, the subsequent inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3F\left(\frac{5\omega+\rho}{6}\right) + 2F\left(\frac{\omega+\rho}{2}\right) + 3F\left(\frac{\omega+5\rho}{6}\right) \right] - \frac{1}{\rho-\omega} \int_{\omega}^{\rho} F(\eta) d\eta \right| \leq \frac{7}{51840} \|F^{(4)}\|_{\infty} (\rho-\omega)^4.$$

The definitions and mathematical preliminaries mentioned below will be frequently used throughout this study.

Definition 1 The incomplete gamma function and the λ -incomplete gamma function can be defined as:

$$\Upsilon(\alpha, x) = \int_0^x t^{\alpha-1} e^{-t} dt$$

and

$$\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, x) = \int_0^x t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda t} dt.$$

Here, $0 < \alpha < \infty$ and $\lambda \geq 0$.

The properties of the λ -incomplete gamma function stated as follows:

Remark 1. [26] For the real numbers $\alpha > 0, \lambda \geq 0$ and $a < b$, we have

$$1. \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) = \int_0^1 t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\rho-\omega)t} dt \frac{1}{(\rho-\omega)^{\alpha}} \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \rho - \omega),$$

$$2. \int_0^1 \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, x) dx = \frac{\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \rho-\omega)}{(\rho-\omega)^{\alpha}} - \frac{\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha+1, \rho-\omega)}{(\rho-\omega)^{\alpha+1}}.$$

Definition 2 (See [13, 23]). A function F defined on the interval $[\omega, \rho]$, consider $F \in L_1[\omega, \rho]$, the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral of order $\alpha > 0$, defined as follows:

$$J_{\omega+}^{\alpha} F(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\omega}^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} F(t) dt, \quad (x > \omega)$$

and

$$J_{\rho-}^{\alpha} F(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^{\rho} (t-x)^{\alpha-1} F(t) dt, \quad x < \rho.$$

Here, $\Gamma(\alpha)$ is the Gamma function and $J_{\omega+}^0 F(x) = J_{\rho-}^0 F(x) = F(x)$.

Definition 3 (See [24, 32]). Tempered fractional integral operators are defined as:

$$3_{\omega+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\omega}^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(x-t)} F(t) dt, \quad x \in [\omega, \rho]$$

and

$$3_{\rho-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^{\rho} (t-x)^{\alpha-1} F(t) dt, \quad x \in [\omega, \rho].$$

Here, $F \in L_1[\omega, \rho], \alpha > 0$ and $\lambda \geq 0$.

If we set $\lambda = 0$ in Definition 3, we get Definition 2 quickly.

To learn more about the various applications of tempered fractional integrals, look into the following books: [25, 29, 30].

Fractional calculus generalizes classical calculus by providing differentiation and integration of non-integer orders, and it is strongly associated with inequality theory. The significance of these inequalities is essential in the examination of diverse mathematical and physical phenomena, encompassing the dynamics of complex systems and the characteristics of particular functions. Moreover, fractional calculus has attracted considerable interest from researchers in diverse disciplines because of its key properties and its application in addressing real-world challenges. As a result, many scholars have formulated a variety of inequalities related to fractional integrals. One can consider tempered fractional calculus as a generalization of fractional calculus. Buschman's prior work first reported the definitions of fractional integration with weak singular and exponential kernels [3]. Rehman et al. [28] proposed novel

inequalities for convex functions utilising tempered fractional integrals. They obtained new results by investigating the relationship between the tempered fractional and the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral. In [26], authors established a notion for λ -incomplete gamma functions. Using this unique notion, they obtained various Hermite-Hadamard inequalities. A novel identity for computing tempered fractional integrals that pertain to twice-differentiable functions is provided by Hezenci and Budak [19]. Utilizing this approach, they established several left Hermite-Hadamard-type inequalities within the framework of the tempered fractional integral. The study of Milne-type inequalities via tempered fractional integrals was conducted by Haider et al. [20]. Additionally, they examined different categories of functions, including convex functions, bounded functions, Lipschitzian functions, and functions of bounded variation. Using Riemann Liouville fractional integrals, Almoneef et al. [2] proved weighted Newton-type inequalities for numerous function classes. Significant integral identities have been obtained using a positive weighted function, resulting in inequality for differentiable convex, bounded, Lipschitzian, and bounded variation functions.

Hezenci and Budak [18] have generalized Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities for differentiable convex functions in the context of tempered fractional integrals. They established a novel identity that involves tempered fractional integrals. By leveraging this identity, they examine various function classes for convex functions.

Lemma 1 (See [18]). Suppose $\mathcal{F}: [\omega, \rho] \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}$ is an absolutely continuous function on the interval (ω, ρ) with $\mathcal{F}' \in L_1[\omega, \rho]$. Then, we have the following Maclaurin-type equality is specifically tailored for tempered fractional integral is valid:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{8} \left[3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{5\omega+\rho}{6} \right) + 2\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega+\rho}{2} \right) + 3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega+5\rho}{6} \right) \right] - \\ & \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \rho-\omega)} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{\rho^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\omega) + \mathfrak{I}_{\omega^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\rho) \right] \\ & = \frac{(\rho-\omega)^{\alpha+1}}{2\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \rho-\omega)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} (\gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t)) [\mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \mathcal{F}'(t\omega + (1-t)\rho)] dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{5}{6}} (\gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \right. \\ & \quad \left. \frac{3}{8} \gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1)) [\mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) - \mathcal{F}'(t\omega + (1-t)\rho)] dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{5}{8}}^{\frac{5}{6}} (\gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \right. \\ & \quad \left. \frac{5}{8} \gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1)) [\mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) - \mathcal{F}'(t\omega + (1-t)\rho)] dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 (\gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \right. \\ & \quad \left. \gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1)) [\mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) - \mathcal{F}'(t\omega + (1-t)\rho)] dt \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Motivated by ongoing investigations, leveraging Lemma 1, we extend new Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities for diverse function classes (bounded and Lipschitzian functions) using tempered fractional integrals. The study is divided into four sections, with the introduction and preliminaries being the first, which includes fundamental definitions of fractional calculus and studies related to research in this field. Section 2, presents various Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities for differentiable convex functions using tempered fractional integrals. Section 3 will include various examples to illustrate these inequalities, emphasizing their practical applications and significance. Finally, in Section 4, we address Euler-Maclaurin inequalities and their potential impact on future research.

2. Main Results

Theorem 4. Given the conditions stipulated in Lemma 1 satisfied. If there exist $m, M \in \mathfrak{R}$ such that $m \leq \mathcal{F}'(t) \leq M$ for $t \in [\omega, \rho]$. Then, we have the following Maclaurin-type inequality is specifically tailored for tempered fractional integral is valid:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{5\omega+\rho}{6} \right) + 2\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega+\rho}{2} \right) + \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. 3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega+5\rho}{6} \right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \rho-\omega)} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{\rho^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\omega) + \mathfrak{I}_{\omega^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\rho) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\rho-\omega)^{\alpha+1}}{2\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \rho-\omega)} [\kappa_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \kappa_2(\alpha, \lambda) + \\ & \kappa_3(\alpha, \lambda) + \kappa_4(\alpha, \lambda)] (M - m), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_1(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} |\gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t)| dt, \\ \kappa_2(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{3}{8} \gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ \kappa_3(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{5}{8} \gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ \kappa_4(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 |\gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1)| dt. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. From Lemma 1, it is easy to write

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{8} \left[3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{5\omega+\rho}{6} \right) + 2\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega+\rho}{2} \right) + 3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega+5\rho}{6} \right) \right] - \\ & \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \rho-\omega)} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{\rho^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\omega) + \mathfrak{I}_{\omega^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\rho) \right] \\ & = \frac{(\rho-\omega)^{\alpha+1}}{2\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \rho-\omega)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} (\gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t)) \left[\mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left(\gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{3}{8} \gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{5}{8}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left(\gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{5}{8} \gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left(\gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \gamma_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \right]. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{5}{8} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \\
 & + \int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) \right) \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\omega + (1-t)\rho) \right] dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{3}{8} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\omega + (1-t)\rho) \right] dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{5}{8} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\omega + (1-t)\rho) \right] dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\omega + (1-t)\rho) \right] dt.
 \end{aligned}$$

Utilizing the modulus properties in above inequality, we can deduce

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5\omega+\rho}{6}\right) + 2\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\omega+\rho}{2}\right) + 3\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\omega+5\rho}{6}\right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \rho-\omega)} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{\rho^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\omega) + \mathfrak{I}_{\omega^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\rho) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{(\rho-\omega)^{\alpha+1}}{2\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \rho-\omega)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} |\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t)| \left| \mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \right. \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{3}{8} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{5}{8} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 |\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1)| \left| \mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \\
 & + \int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} |\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t)| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\omega + (1-t)\rho) \right| dt
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{3}{8} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\omega + (1-t)\rho) \right| dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{5}{8} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\omega + (1-t)\rho) \right| dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\omega + (1-t)\rho) \right| dt.
 \end{aligned}$$

Based on the given assumption $m \leq \mathcal{F}'(t) \leq M$ for $t \in [\omega, \rho]$, it yields

$$\left| \mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| \leq \frac{M-m}{2} \quad (6)$$

and

$$\left| \frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\omega + (1-t)\rho) \right| \leq \frac{M-m}{2}. \quad (7)$$

With the help of inequality (6) and (7), we acquire

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5\omega+\rho}{6}\right) + 2\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\omega+\rho}{2}\right) + 3\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\omega+5\rho}{6}\right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \rho-\omega)} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{\rho^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\omega) + \mathfrak{I}_{\omega^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\rho) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{(\rho-\omega)^{\alpha+1}}{2\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \rho-\omega)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} |\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t)| dt \right. \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{3}{8} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{5}{8} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 |\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1)| dt \left. \right] \\
 & \quad (M-m) \\
 & = \frac{(\rho-\omega)^{\alpha+1}}{2\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \rho-\omega)} [\kappa_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \kappa_2(\alpha, \lambda) + \kappa_3(\alpha, \lambda) + \kappa_4(\alpha, \lambda)](M-m).
 \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof.

Corollary 1. Taking $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 4, we attain

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5\omega+\rho}{6}\right) + 2\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\omega+\rho}{2}\right) + 3\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\omega+5\rho}{6}\right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(\rho-\omega)^{\alpha}} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{\rho^-}^{\alpha} \mathcal{F}(\omega) + \mathfrak{I}_{\omega^+}^{\alpha} \mathcal{F}(\rho) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{\alpha(\rho-\omega)}{2} [\kappa_1(\alpha, 0) + \kappa_2(\alpha, 0) + \kappa_3(\alpha, 0) + \kappa_4(\alpha, 0)](M-m).
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 2. By substituting $\lambda = 0$, $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 4, we attain

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{5\omega + \rho}{6} \right) + 2\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega + \rho}{2} \right) + 3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega + 5\rho}{6} \right) \right] - \frac{1}{\rho - \omega} \int_{\omega}^{\rho} \mathcal{F}(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{25(\rho - \omega)}{576} (M - m),$$

which is presented in [15, Corollary 2].

Corollary 2. Given the conditions specified in Theorem 4, for any t within the range $[\omega, \rho]$, assuming the existence of a positive constant M satisfying $|\mathcal{F}'(t)| \leq M$, it yields

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{5\omega + \rho}{6} \right) + 2\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega + \rho}{2} \right) + 3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega + 5\rho}{6} \right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \rho - \omega)} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{\rho^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\omega) + \mathfrak{I}_{\omega^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\rho) \right] \right| \leq \frac{(\rho - \omega)^{\alpha+1}}{\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \rho - \omega)} [\kappa_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \kappa_2(\alpha, \lambda) + \kappa_3(\alpha, \lambda) + \kappa_4(\alpha, \lambda)] M.$$

Corollary 3. If we take $\lambda = 0$, in Corollary 2, we acquire

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{5\omega + \rho}{6} \right) + 2\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega + \rho}{2} \right) + 3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega + 5\rho}{6} \right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(\rho - \omega)^{\alpha}} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{\rho^-}^{\alpha} \mathcal{F}(\omega) + \mathfrak{I}_{\omega^+}^{\alpha} \mathcal{F}(\rho) \right] \right| \leq \alpha(\rho - \omega) [\kappa_1(\alpha, 0) + \kappa_2(\alpha, 0) + \kappa_3(\alpha, 0) + \kappa_4(\alpha, 0)] M.$$

Remark 3. Let $\lambda = 0, \alpha = 1$ in Corollary 2, it yields

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{5\omega + \rho}{6} \right) + 2\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega + \rho}{2} \right) + 3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega + 5\rho}{6} \right) \right] - \frac{1}{\rho - \omega} \int_{\omega}^{\rho} \mathcal{F}(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{25(\rho - \omega)}{288} M,$$

which is reported in [15, Corollary 4].

Theorem 5. Given the conditions stipulated in Lemma 1 hold. If \mathcal{F}' is an Lipschitzian function on the interval $[\omega, \rho]$. Then, we have the following Maclaurin-type inequality is specifically tailored for tempered fractional integral is valid:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{5\omega + \rho}{6} \right) + 2\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega + \rho}{2} \right) + 3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega + 5\rho}{6} \right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \rho - \omega)} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{\rho^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\omega) + \mathfrak{I}_{\omega^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\rho) \right] \right| \leq \frac{(\rho - \omega)^{\alpha+2}}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \rho - \omega)} [\kappa_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \kappa_2(\alpha, \lambda) - \kappa_3(\alpha, \lambda) - \kappa_4(\alpha, \lambda) - 2(\kappa_5(\alpha, \lambda) + \kappa_6(\alpha, \lambda)) + 2(\kappa_7(\alpha, \lambda) + \kappa_8(\alpha, \lambda))] L,$$

where $\kappa_1(\alpha, \lambda), \kappa_2(\alpha, \lambda), \kappa_3(\alpha, \lambda)$ and $\kappa_4(\alpha, \lambda)$ are defined as in Theorem 2, and

$$\kappa_5(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} t |\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t)| dt,$$

$$\kappa_6(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{2}} t \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{3}{8} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt,$$

$$\kappa_7(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{5}{6}} t \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{5}{8} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt,$$

$$\kappa_8(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 t |\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1)| dt.$$

Proof. By utilizing modulus in Lemma 1, we acquire

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{5\omega + \rho}{6} \right) + 2\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega + \rho}{2} \right) + 3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega + 5\rho}{6} \right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \rho - \omega)} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{\rho^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\omega) + \mathfrak{I}_{\omega^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\rho) \right] \right| \leq \frac{(\rho - \omega)^{\alpha+1}}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \rho - \omega)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} |\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t)| |\mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) - \mathcal{F}'(t\omega + (1-t)\rho)| dt + \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{3}{8} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) - \mathcal{F}'(t\omega + (1-t)\rho)| dt + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{5}{8} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) - \mathcal{F}'(t\omega + (1-t)\rho)| dt + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 |\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1)| |\mathcal{F}'(t\rho + (1-t)\omega) - \mathcal{F}'(t\omega + (1-t)\rho)| dt \right].$$

As $|\mathcal{F}'|$ is L-Lipschitzian function, we can conclude

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{5\omega + \rho}{6} \right) + 2\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega + \rho}{2} \right) + 3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega + 5\rho}{6} \right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \rho - \omega)} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{\rho^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\omega) + \mathfrak{I}_{\omega^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\rho) \right] \right| \leq \frac{(\rho - \omega)^{\alpha+1}}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \rho - \omega)} \left[\left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} |\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t)| dt + \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{3}{8} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right) L(1-2t)(\rho - \omega) + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{5}{8} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 |\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, t) - \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\omega)}(\alpha, 1)| dt \right) L(2t-1)(\rho - \omega) \right]$$

$$= \frac{(\rho - \omega)^{\alpha+2}}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \rho - \omega)} [\kappa_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \kappa_2(\alpha, \lambda) - \kappa_3(\alpha, \lambda) - \kappa_4(\alpha, \lambda) - 2(\kappa_5(\alpha, \lambda) + \kappa_6(\alpha, \lambda)) + 2(\kappa_7(\alpha, \lambda) + \kappa_8(\alpha, \lambda))] L.$$

This concludes the proof.

Corollary 4. Assume $\lambda = 0$, in Theorem 5, we acquire

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{5\omega + \rho}{6} \right) + 2\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega + \rho}{2} \right) + 3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega + 5\rho}{6} \right) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(\rho - \omega)^\alpha} [3\rho^\alpha \mathcal{F}(\omega) + 3\omega^\alpha \mathcal{F}(\rho)] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\alpha(\rho - \omega)^2}{2} [\kappa_1(\alpha, 0) + \kappa_2(\alpha, 0) - \kappa_3(\alpha, 0) - \kappa_4(\alpha, 0) \\ & \quad - 2(\kappa_5(\alpha, 0) + \kappa_6(\alpha, 0)) \\ & \quad + 2(\kappa_7(\alpha, 0) + \kappa_8(\alpha, 0))]L. \end{aligned}$$

Remark 4. Assume $\lambda = 0, \alpha = 1$ in Theorem 5, it yields

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{5\omega + \rho}{6} \right) + 2\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega + \rho}{2} \right) + 3\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\omega + 5\rho}{6} \right) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{1}{\rho - \omega} \int_\omega^\rho \mathcal{F}(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{475(\rho - \omega)^2}{20736} L, \end{aligned}$$

which is identified in [15, Corollary 5].

Numerical Examples

Example 1 Suppose a functions $F(t) = \frac{t^2}{2}$, in Theorem 4 for all $t > 0, \lambda = 1, \alpha > 0, \omega = 0, \rho = 1, m = -1$ and $M = 1$ then we observe the following numerical verification (see Table 1 and corresponding graph (see Figure 1)).

Table 1: Numerical values of Theorem 2 for $\mathcal{F}(t) = \frac{t^2}{2}, \omega = 0, \rho = 1$ and $\lambda = 1$.

α	Left Term	Right Term
0.1	0.0710048976	0.4408549130
0.2	0.0672624073	0.3871709388
0.3	0.0635235377	0.3384137147
0.4	0.0598277302	0.2940911104
0.5	0.0562030958	0.2537549816
0.6	0.0526691084	0.2170004906
0.7	0.0492387017	0.1834639718
0.8	0.0459198909	2.3174314425
0.9	0.0427170216	2.7160668219

Figure 1: Comparative analysis of inequalities (6), for $\mathcal{F}(t) = \frac{t^2}{2}, \omega = 0$ and $\rho = 1$, when λ is fixed and α lies between 0 and 1.

Conclusion

Throughout this investigation, we extend the work of Hezenci and Budak by deriving new Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities through tempered fractional integrals. The inequalities obtained for bounded and Lipschitzian functions in the framework of tempered fractional calculus. These inequalities are demonstrated to be relevant in numerical analysis and other fields by the specific cases that are analyzed, which serve as illustrations of their practical applications. Future research may investigate new function classes and refine these inequalities, increasing their applicability in a variety of mathematical contexts. Readers can further expand on our findings by applying a different kind of fractional integral.

Declaration of Ethical Standards

The author(s) of this article declares that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and/or legal-special permission.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

References

[1] Ali, M. A., Budak, H., Abbas, M., Sarikaya, M. Z., & Kashuri, A. (2019). New inequalities of Hermite-Hadamard type for h -convex functions via generalized fractional integrals. *Journal of Mathematical Extension*, 14, 187-234.

- [2] Almongeef, A. A., Hyder, A. A., & Budak, H. (2024). Deriving weighted Newton-type inequalities for diverse function classes through Riemann Liouville fractional integrals. *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, 186, 115205.
- [3] Buschman, R. G. (1972). Decomposition of an integral operator by use of Mikusinski calculus. *SIAM Journal on Mathematical Analysis*, 3(1), 83-85.
- [4] Budak, H., Kara, H., Sarikaya, M. Z., & Kiris, M. E. (2020). New extensions of the Hermite-Hadamard inequalities involving Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. *Miskolc Mathematical Notes*, 21(2), 665-678.
- [5] Dragomir, S. S. (1999). On Simpson's quadrature formula for mappings of bounded variation and applications. *Tamkang Journal of Mathematics*, 30(1), 53-58.
- [6] Davis P.J., & Rabinowitz P. (1975). *Methods of numerical integration*. Academic Press, New York-San Francisco-London.
- [7] Dedic L. J., Matic M., & Pecaric. J., (2003). Euler Maclaurin formulae. *Mathematics Inequalities and applications*, 6(2):247-275.
- [8] Dwilewicz, R. J. (2009). A short history of Convexity. *Differential Geometry-Dynamical Systems*.
- [9] Dedic ,L., Matic , M., Pevcaric, J., & Vukelic, A. (2011). On Euler-Simpson $3/8$ formulae. *Nonlinear studies*, 18(1), 1-26.
- [10] Erden, S., Iftikhar, S., Kumam, P., & Awan, M. U. (2020). Some Newton like inequalities with applications. *Revista de la Real Academia de Ciencias Exactas, Fisicas y Naturales. Serie A. Matematicas*, 114, 1-13.
- [11] Franjic, I., Pecaric, J., Peric, I., & Vukelic, A. (2011). Euler integral identity, quadrature formulae and error estimations. *Element*.
- [12] Franjic, I., & Pecaric, J. (2005). Corrected Euler-Maclaurin formulae. *Rendiconti del Circolo Matematico di Palermo*, 54, 259-272.
- [13] Gorenflo, R., & Mainardi, F. (1997). *Fractional calculus: Integral and differential equations of fractional order*, Springer Vienna.
- [14] Gao, S., & Shi, W. (2012). On new inequalities of Newton type for functions whose second derivatives absolute values are convex. *Int. J. Pure Appl. Math*, 74(1), 33-41.
- [15] Gümüs, M., Hezenci, F. & Budak, H. (2024). Some New Approaches to Fractional Euler -Maclaurin-Type Inequalities via Various Function Classes. *Fractal and Fractional*, 8(7): 372.
- [16] Hezenci, F., & Budak, H. (2023). Some Perturbed Newton type inequalities for Riemann Liouville fractional integrals. *Rocky Mountain Journal of Mathematics*, 53(4), 1117-1127.
- [17] Hezenci, F., Budak, H., & Kosem, P. (2023). A New version of Newtons Inequalities for Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. *Rocky Mountain Journal of Mathematics*, 53(1), 49-64.
- [18] Hezenci, F., & Budak, H. (2024). Some Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities by means of tempered fractional integrals. *Journal of Nonlinear Modeling and Analysis*, accepted, in press.
- [19] Hezenci, F., & Budak, H. (2023.) Midpoint-type inequalities via twice-differentiable functions on tempered fractional integrals. *Journal of Inequality and Applications*, 150.
- [20] Haider, W., Budak, H., Shehzadi, A., Hezenci, F., & Chen, H. (2024). A comprehensive study on Milne-type inequalities with tempered fractional integrals. *Boundary Value Problems*, 2024(1), 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13661-024-01855-1>.
- [21] Hezenci, F. & Budak, H. (2022). Maclaurin-type inequalities for Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. *Ann. Univ. Mariae Curie-Sklodowska Sect. A Mathematics*, 2022, 76, 15-32.
- [22] Iftikhar, S., Kumam, P., & Erden, S. (2020). Newtons-type integral inequalities via local fractional integrals. *Fractals*, 28(03), 2050037.
- [23] Kilbas, A. A., Srivastava, H. M., & Trujillo, J. J. (2006). *Theory and applications of fractional differential equations*. Elsevier, 204.
- [24] Li, C., Deng, W., & Zhao, L. (2015). Well-posedness and numerical algorithm for the tempered fractional ordinary differential equations. arXiv preprint arXiv:1501.00376.
- [25] Meerschaert, M. M., Sabzikar, F., & Chen, J. (2015). Tempered fractional calculus. *Journal of computational physics*, 293, 14.
- [26] Mohammed, P. O., Sarikaya, M. Z., & Baleanu, D. (2020). On the generalized Hermite Hadamard inequalities via the tempered fractional integrals. *Symmetry*, 12(4), 595.

- [27] Meftah, B. (2023). Maclaurin type inequalities for multiplicatively convex functions. *Proceedings of the American Mathematical Society*, 151(05), 2115-2125.
- [28] Rahman, G., Nisar, K. S., & Abdeljawad, T. (2020). Tempered fractional integral inequalities for convex functions. *Mathematics*, 8(4), 500.
- [29] Srivastava, H. M. & Buschman, R. G. (1977). Convolution integral equations, with special function kernels. New York: Wiley.
- [30] Samko, S. G. (1993). Fractional integrals and derivatives. *Theory and applications*.
- [31] Sarikaya, M. Z., Set, E., Yaldiz, H., & Basak, N. (2013). Hermite Hadamard inequalities for fractional integrals and related fractional inequalities. *Mathematical and Computer Modelling*, 57(9-10), 2403-2407.
- [32] Sabzikar, F., Meerschaert, M. M., & Chen, J. (2015). Tempered fractional calculus. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 293, 14-28.
- [33] Sitthiwiratham, T., Nonlaopon, K., Ali, M. A., & Budak, H. (2022). Riemann Liouville fractional Newton type inequalities for differentiable convex functions. *Fractal and Fractional*, 6(3), 175.
- [34] Shehzadi, A., Budak, H., Haider, W., & Chen, H. (2024). Milne-type Inequalities for co-ordinated Convex Functions. *Filomat*, Vol 38, No 23 (2024).